

Risk and Return Analysis of Equity Shares with Special Reference to Companies (BSE) Stock Index

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Abstract

Analysis of risk and return of individual stock is primary steps of every investor before making investment. The main purpose of individual investor is maximizing wealth in a low level of risk. But it is very difficult to find out such investment avenue from the pool of investment avenues. In Bombay stock exchanges there are more than 5500 companies listed and 30 companies are considered as blue chip companies. This paper studies about risk and return analysis of these blue chip companies. Here data were collected highly authenticated websites such as BSE official website and money control.com. In order to analyze the risk and return of individual stock some of the statistical tools were used like Standard deviation, Correlation and CAPM model. The main objective of this paper is to find out risk return parity in the individual companies which are considered in the calculation of SENSEX index.

Key Factor: Risk and return, Volatility of share price.

INTRODUCTION:

Whether it is investing, driving or just walking down the street, everyone exposes themselves to risk. Managing risk plays vital role. Same in case of investment, every investment avenues has some sort of risk. Risk is defined as the chance that an investment's actual return will be different than expected. This includes the possibility of losing some or all of the original investment. Normally investors expect high rate of return with low level risk. But in practical life there is high levels of uncertainty (high risk) are associated with high potential returns. The risk/return tradeoff is the balance between the desire for the lowest possible risk and the highest possible return. In finance, return is a profit on an investment. It comprises any change in value and interest or dividends or other such cash flows which the investor receives from the investment. It may be measured either in absolute terms (e.g., dollars) or as a percentage of the amount invested. There are many factors which will affect invest decision but in this paper only factor considered that is 'Risk' and 'Return'. Researcher analyses these two factors of every companies listed in Sensex (Blue Chip companies) and give suggestion for better investment plan.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The core objective of this study is to analyze the risk and return of 30 top stocks listed on BSE. However in order to achieve the main objective, the following specific objectives have been framed:

- ✚ To study the variation in the stock returns for the study period of one years.
- ✚ To rank the companies on the basis of return and risk
- ✚ To offer meaningful suggestions to the investors based on the findings of the study.

SCOPE OF STUDY

The study examines the stock returns of 30 top companies listed on BSE during the period, from 23rd May 2016 to 23rd May 2017. The study covers the risk return analysis of 30 top listed companies only.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is purely based on secondary data collected from BSE Web Site and Money Control.com. The yearly share prices of 30 top companies listed on BSE, which are used to compile BSE SENSEX, are collected from May 2016 to May 2017. These data are used to calculate actual return, CAPM return and abnormal return of each of the 30 companies. Then, 30 companies are ranked according to the returns yielded by them. Standard deviations and coefficient of variation of these 30 companies are arrived at to rank them based on risk. This information is presented through tables.

TECHNIQUES OF ANALYSIS

Actual Return

Actual returns for each company have been computed for the study period as under:

$$R_i = \frac{P_1 - P_0}{P_0}$$

Where, r_i is return on individual security, P_1 = Market price (closing) of security and P_0 = Market price of security on day (t-1).

Comparatively, the actual returns for the market are also computed as:

$$R_m = \frac{P_1 - P_0}{P_0}$$

Where r_m is return on market, P_1 is closing market return and P_0 market return in the beginning. In the next step, average actual returns of individual stocks and market return is computed.

CAPM Return

CAPM return is calculated by applying the following formulae:

$$\bar{r}_a = r_f + \beta_a(\bar{r}_m - r_f)$$

Where:

r_f = Risk free rate

β_a = Beta of the security

\bar{r}_m = Expected market return

Beta of the security is calculated with the help of the following formula:

$$\beta_p = \frac{\text{Cov}(r_p, r_b)}{\text{Var}(r_b)}$$

Abnormal Returns

Abnormal return is the excess of the actual return over the expected return. It is calculated as under:

Abnormal Return = Actual Return – CAPM Return

Standard Deviation

It measures the amount of variation from the average. A low standard deviation indicates that the data points tend to be very close to the mean (also called expected value); a high standard deviation indicates that the data points are spread out over a large range of values.

$$\text{S.D.} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2}{n}}$$

Where: $\sum X^2$ = The sum of the squares of the differences between the Mean and each score

n = The number of scores

Coefficient of Variation

The coefficient of variation represents the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean, and it is a useful statistic for comparing the degree of variation from one data series to another, even if the means are drastically different from each other.

$$\text{Coefficient of Variation} = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}}{\text{Expected Return}}$$

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

Every research has its own limitations. The following are the limitations of this study:

- ✚ The study covers only 30 listed companies of BSE
- ✚ This study is limited to the analysis of risk and return of 30 stocks.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data are collected various sources and analyzed following way in order to interpret result. The following interpretation are purely based on researcher knowledge.

Return Analysis

Return expresses the amount which an investor actually earned on an investment during a certain period. Return includes the interest, dividend and capital gains. Following table shows the actual return, CAPM return and abnormal return of individual securities and they are ranked according their return.

Table 1: Rank of the BSE 30 Companies according to Actual, CAPM and Abnormal Return

Sl.No	Company Name	Actual return	Rank	CAPM return	Rank	Abnormal return	Rank
1	Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Ltd.	0.8508	1	0.271395	5	0.579405	1
2	Asian Paints Ltd.	0.1604	18	0.39067	1	-0.23027	25
3	Axis Bank Ltd.	0.0342	22	0.300755	2	-0.266555	27
4	Bajaj Auto Ltd.	0.1775	16	0.205335	13	-0.027835	17
5	Bharti Airtel Ltd.	0.0775	21	0.203133	14	-0.125633	22
6	Cipla Ltd.	0.0816	20	0.1780855	18	-0.096485	18
7	Coal India Ltd.	-0.0323	26	0.20717	12	-0.23947	26
8	Dr. Reddys Laboratories Ltd.	-0.1565	28	0.13982	27	-0.29632	29
9	GAIL (India) Ltd.	0.3519	9	0.17689	19	0.17501	8
10	HDFC Bank Ltd.	0.3832	8	0.201298	15	0.181902	6
11	Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	0.2396	15	0.175241	20	0.064359	15
12	Hindustan Unilever Ltd.	0.2539	14	0.173406	22	0.080494	13
13	Housing Development Finance Corporation Ltd	0.3093	11	0.227355	9	0.081945	12
14	ICICI Bank Ltd.	0.3879	7	0.282405	3	0.105495	10
15	Infosys Ltd.	-0.1969	29	-0.037619	30	-0.15981	24
16	ITC Ltd.	0.2963	12	0.209005	11	0.087895	11
17	Larsen & Toubro Ltd.	0.4059	6	0.22552	10	0.18038	7

18	Lupin Ltd.	-0.1553	27	0.138908	28	-0.294208	28
19	Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	0.0326	23	0.147165	24	-0.114565	21
20	Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	0.7506	2	0.175241	21	0.575359	2
21	NTPC Ltd.	0.1559	19	0.1405595	26	0.0153405	16
22	Oil & Natural Gas Corporation Ltd.	0.2601	13	0.1857005	16	0.0743995	14
23	Power Grid Corporation Of India Ltd.	0.3506	10	0.1526705	23	0.1979295	5
24	Reliance Industries Ltd.	0.4103	5	0.2402	7	0.1701	9
25	State Bank Of India	0.7129	3	0.278735	4	0.434165	3
26	Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd.	-0.2244	30	0.234695	8	-0.459095	30
27	Tata Consultancy Services Ltd.	0.0131	24	0.142945	25	-0.129845	23
28	Tata Motors Ltd.	0.1672	17	0.264055	6	-0.096855	19
29	Tata Steel Ltd.	0.5706	4	0.1831315	17	0.3874685	4
30	Wipro Ltd.	-0.0266	25	0.0796375	29	-0.106238	20

Source: Authors compilation

From the above table it is clear that Adani ports and special economic zone ltd got first rank as per actual return and abnormal return and Maruthi Suzuki India ltd got second rank in the both actual return and abnormal return. It is surprised that Infosys Company which is one of the top IT sector has negative return and got 29th rank in the actual return and 30th rank in the CAPM return. When we look at CAPM return Asian paints ltd got first rank and Axis bank ltd placed at second rank. Tata steel has highest actual return and it is placed in the fourth Rank and it's expected return (CAPM) is very low (Ranked at 17) therefore it's abnormal return become more, it ranked fourth place. In Banking Industry State Bank of India which is largest bank in India has better actual return (Placed at 3rd Rank), CAPM return (Placed at 4th Rank) and abnormal return (Placed at 3rd Rank). In Oil industries ONGC has great track record but in this year it is recorded moderate return and placed 13th rank. One of the top companies in the FMCG industry is ITC ltd. which placed 12th Rank in actual return.

Risk analysis

Many time individual investors end up with loss, this is because of various reasons. One of the main reasons is inability of managing risk. Every stock has some sort of risk but investor has to analyze risk and return before investment. Therefore the following table shows standard deviation and coefficient variances in order analyze the risk of individual security and ranked according to their risk or volatility (Lowest to highest)

Table 2: Rank of the NSE 30 Companies according to Standard deviation and Coefficient of variation

Sl.No	Company Name	S.D	Mean	Coefficient Variance	Rank
1	Adani Ports and Special Economic Zone Ltd.	9.78	255.17	0.0383	3
2	Asian Paints Ltd.	15.11	878.54	0.0172	14
3	Axis Bank Ltd.	9.07	436.10	0.0208	13
4	Bajaj Auto Ltd.	7.14	2370.97	0.0030	26
5	Bharti Airtel Ltd.	7.52	348.61	0.0216	12
6	Cipla Ltd.	6.69	543.91	0.0123	16
7	Coal India Ltd.	8.20	325.95	0.0252	10
8	Dr. Reddys Laboratories Ltd.	7.75	3032.34	0.0026	29
9	GAIL (India) Ltd.	7.98	295.59	0.0270	9
10	HDFC Bank Ltd.	5.13	1008.31	0.0051	24
11	Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	6.62	2427.64	0.0027	28
12	Hindustan Unilever Ltd.	7.24	781.09	0.0093	18
13	Housing Development Finance Corporation Ltd	6.15	1143.11	0.0054	22
14	ICICI Bank Ltd.	8.42	268.11	0.0314	7
15	Infosys Ltd.	8.01	929.23	0.0086	19
16	ITC Ltd.	7.63	232.77	0.0328	6
17	Larsen & Toubro Ltd.	9.61	1406.11	0.0068	21
18	Lupin Ltd.	7.47	1411.31	0.0053	23
19	Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	5.70	1200.56	0.0047	25
20	Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	6.86	3669.54	0.0019	30
21	NTPC Ltd.	7.04	143.26	0.0491	1
22	Oil & Natural Gas Corporation Ltd.	7.10	196.51	0.0361	5
23	Power Grid Corporation Of India Ltd.	5.36	142.84	0.0375	4
24	Reliance Industries Ltd.	7.65	982.69	0.0078	20
25	State Bank Of India	9.64	235.72	0.0409	2
26	Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd.	11.55	758.84	0.0152	15
27	Tata Consultancy Services Ltd.	6.61	2376.72	0.0028	27
28	Tata Motors Ltd.	9.57	439.70	0.0218	11

29	Tata Steel Ltd.	10.60	372.14	0.0285	8
30	Wipro Ltd.	6.26	536.66	0.0117	17

Source: Authors compilation

From the above table it is clear that NTPC Ltd, State Bank of India, Adani ports and economic zone ltd., Power Grid corporation of India Ltd. have very low level of volatility, it means its fluctuation in return is very low and invariably these companies are low risk companies. Maruthi Suzuki India ltd., Dr. Reddys' laboratories ltd, Hero MotoCorp Ltd., Tata Consultancy Services Ltd, Bajaj Auto Ltd have high volatility, therefore it has high risk. Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd, Cipla Ltd., Wipro Ltd., Hindustan Unilever Ltd., Infosys Ltd. have moderate risk. Investment decision depends upon capability of taking risk, if investor risk taker then he can go for high risk companies.

FINDINGS:

This part of the study speaks about the major findings of the study:

- ✚ It is clear that Adani ports and special economic zone ltd. has gained highest actual return and abnormal return during the considered year.
- ✚ It finds that Asian Paints ltd. has achieved highest CAPM return than other stocks in the list.
- ✚ It is clear that Infosys ltd has achieved lowest actual return, CAPM return and abnormal return.
- ✚ It is found that NTPC ltd. has achieved highest volatility.
- ✚ Maruthi Suzuki India ltd. has involved highest risk.
- ✚ It is clear that Adani ports and special economic zone ltd. gives highest return at low rate of risk.
- ✚ It is clear that Sun Pharmaceuticals Industries ltd. has gives least return at moderate risk.
- ✚ It is found that Dr. Reddys Laboratories ltd. gives low return at a low level of risk.

SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

Equity analysis is the most important measurement technique used to measure the movement of share market, which helps the investor to take decision either to buy or sell. Long term investors were able to take advantage of the market as it less volatile. As there is less fluctuation in the shares when compared to market as well as its prices, the long term investors able to predict about when the share will raise. Those who want to earn high return at a low risk it is best to invest in Adani ports and special economic Zone ltd. Those that are ready to take high risk and wanted to earn high return they can invest Maruthi Suzuki India ltd. Who wants to invest at a moderate of return they can go for Hero motor corp. ltd. Invest decision is always depends upon

individual capacity. If you want to become a successful investor you need to study the equity market on a daily basis. Analyse the market trend and next take investment decision is the best motto of an intelligent investor.

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